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DEMANDS OF THE LABOUR MARKET IN THE NETHERLANDS AND THE EU BLUE CARD: LIMITATIONS AND OPPORTUNITIES

Abstract:

An ageing society, rapid technological developments combined with an increasing demand for (highly) skilled workers places the EU for great challenges. To implement and bring the EU Blue Card into practice was a means to partly alleviate the demand at least for the highly skilled labour and a first step to increase the attractiveness of the EU labour market. However, current researches show that the impact of the Blue Card is limited. There is a variety of conditions set by the Member States (MS) which diminishes a user friendly procedure for highly skilled migrant workers. Furthermore, MS were allowed to develop their own national regulations for attracting (highly) skilled workers. This, in particularly the Netherlands led more to priorities in national regulations than to emphasising the Blue Card.

The intentions of the EU to give the Blue Card a boost in the upcoming term will give way for new initiatives. The success of the new Blue Card version though, will also depend on the attention paid to factors that are decisive for migrant workers such as their preference for the nationality of a MS and social aspects in their life that can either decrease or increase the incentive for mobility within the EU. Furthermore, the role of the (HR) division of the employer can be a key factor to make the future migrants aware of the choice between national residence permits and the Blue card. A sole focus on a new or amended set of regulations is however a too narrow starting point. Another aspect is the demand driven mechanism of the Blue Card which leads to individual initiatives of employers whether or not to hire an employee from a third country. This stands in the way of an (additional) macro-economic approach with a supply driven point based system in which sectors with high demands for (highly) skilled workers form the core business. The extent to which this risk avoiding character will be held onto in the near future will affect the way in which the Blue Card will be developed. In conclusion, the success of the future Blue Card will very well depend on the boldness in the EU decision making process and that of the MS to open the economic markets for third country (highly) skilled workers in such a way that labour demands in the next decades can be answered as the quest for a more efficient use of EU labour potential has still not been fulfilled.

Keywords: EU law, labour law, Blue Card, migrant workers, highly skilled workers

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I. INTRODUCTION

The European labour market is confronted with many great challenges¹, such as rapid technological changes and an ageing society. An increasing demand for a highly skilled labour force whereas the existence of an uncertainty about the future growth brings another complication to these challenges. The increasing demand can lead to an assumption that the Member States (MS) install policy instruments to solve (future) shortages on their labour market. However, labour migration from third countries is not structurally used as an instrument to decrease labour shortages in the MS.² With regards to the aspect of mobility it can be stated that theoretically the EU Blue Card has an advantage in comparison with the several national policies in that sense that the possession of the Blue Card enables the migrant to move within the EU labour market under certain preconditions. This leads to the key question to which extent the EU Blue Card can contribute to a decrease in the shortages of (highly) skilled migrants to live and work in the EU and especially in the Netherlands.

It must be noted that although the Blue Card nowadays focuses on highly skilled labour, it should not be ruled out that its emphasis can include skilled workers in the future. With that in mind, information on this particular target group is also incorporated.

The following topics will be discussed. Firstly, the Blue Card and its objective is briefly explained. Secondly, the sectors in the Netherlands with great demands are highlighted after which the present Dutch answers to these demands are explained. Thirdly, the obstacles of the Blue Card are mentioned including the current issues that needs to be taken into account that can offer new insights with regard to the obstacles mentioned. The possible opportunities are the final subject after which the conclusions are presented.

II. EU BLUE CARD

Council Directive 2009/50/EC of 25 May 2009 on the conditions of entry and residence of third-country nationals for the purposes of highly qualified employment, also known as the EU Blue Card, enables the residence of highly qualified employment of third country nationals in the EU. The main conditions are the possession of a valid work contract or binding job offer of at least one year, an agreed salary that has to be at least the threshold set by the individual

¹ K. Attström et.al., *Mapping and Analysing Bottleneck Vacancies in EU Labour Markets*, Rotterdam, Ramboll and SEOR Erasmus School of Economics commissioned by the European Commission, 2014.

² European Migration Network, *Labour market shortages and migration*, Rijswijk, European Commission, 2015

MS³ and the successful completion a post-secondary higher education program⁴ of at least three years. The residence permit is granted for the same duration as your employment contract with a maximum of 5 years.

The Blue Card can be used to enhance mobility within the MS of the European Union. One of the preconditions to attain this mobility is the 18 months of legal residence in the first MS as an EU Blue Card holder before moving to the second one. The latter MS examines the application with its own set of requirements. The card holder and family members are allowed to move to another MS for the purpose of highly qualified employment if the requirements for the Blue Card are met in the latter MS.

After five years of legal and continuous stay in the Netherlands every migrant - also the EU Blue Card holder - may qualify for a permanent EC long term residence permit under Directive 2003/109/EC. The EU Blue Card holder however is allowed to accumulate periods of residence in different MS in order to fulfil the requirements of 5 years of legal and continuous stay.⁵

Absence of the territory of the EU by the EU Blue Card holder is not considered an interruption of the 5 years of legal and continuous stay. This period of absence is shorter than 12 consecutive months and does not exceed in total 18 months.⁶

After this illustration of the set-up of the Blue Card, the next step is to look into the shortages of workers in the EU and particularly in the Netherlands after which a comparison is made to identify to which extent the Blue Card is compatible with the level of skills of the needed labour migrants.

III. SHORTAGES OF (HIGHLY) SKILLED WORKERS IN THE EU AND PARTICULARLY IN THE NETHERLANDS

The table below illustrates the top 20 bottleneck vacancies. The International Standard Classification of Occupations (ISCO)⁷ is used as a common identifier of job classifications in

³ The threshold in the Netherlands is a gross monthly salary of EUR 4,908 (exclusive of 8% holiday allowance) amounting to an annual gross salary of EUR 63,607.68 (including 8% holiday allowance).

⁴ In order to prove this a diploma or certificate has to be submitted. Foreign diplomas must be evaluated by the Dutch organisation IDW (Internationale diplomawaardering).

⁵ Provided, that the applicant has legal and continuous residence for two years immediately prior to the submission within the territory of the MS, where the application for the EC-long term residence permit is lodged.

⁶ These periods of absence are restricted to cases where the EU Blue Card holder has returned to his country of origin to work as an employee, self-employed person, to perform voluntary service, or to study. Once the EC-long term resident status is acquired by the former EU Blue Card holder, they are allowed to be absent of the territory of the European Union for 24 months.

⁷ ISCO is one of the main international classifications for which ILO is responsible.

the EU and shows that not only highly skilled labour, but that also skilled labour are amongst the bottlenecks as well. Examples of high demands in highly skilled labour are science and engineering professionals as well as information and communications technology professionals, and health professionals. Bottlenecks in skilled labour are found in demands for metal, machinery and related trades workers which is ranked on the first place on the list of bottleneck vacancies. In the top 5 are also building and related trades workers, excluding electricians with a higher ranking than science and engineering associate professionals.

Table 1 Top 20 bottleneck vacancies at ISCO 2-digit level European level⁸

Rank at ISCO 2-digit level	ISCO code and description	Rank value ⁹	Number of countries reporting
1	72 Metal, machinery and related trades workers	677	23
2	21 Science and engineering professionals	576	22
3	25 Information and communications technology professionals	530	20
4	22 Health professionals	521	21
5	71 Building and related trades workers, excluding electricians	485	18
6	51 Personal service workers	438	22
7	31 Science and engineering associate professionals	310	14
8	52 Sales workers	257	13
9	83 Drivers and mobile plant operators	252	16
10	75 Food processing, wood working, garment and other craft and related trades workers	237	12
11	23 Teaching professionals	215	12
12	33 Business and administration associate professionals	204	13
13	24 Business and administration professionals	176	11
14	74 Electrical and electronic trades workers	172	12
15	81 Stationary plant and machine operators	155	9
16	91 Cleaners and helpers	145	8
17	96 Refuse workers and other elementary workers	140	5
18	53 Personal care workers	139	6
19	12 Administrative and commercial managers	119	6
20	92 Agricultural, forestry and fishery labourers	112	3

⁸ K. Attström et.al.

⁹ The bottleneck occupations in 18 countries out of 29 countries were identified. The ranking was done by a ranking of a supply-demand ratio, an employer's survey and other possible rankings. The ranking in the Netherlands differed to much from this system and was therefore not compatible with the ranking of other MS and not included in the table above.

In the Netherlands, shortages are concentrated on the sectors of technology, IT and specific niches of chartered accountants for example and district nurses. These shortages are not only seen on the higher and academic level, but on a secondary level as well. This regards inter alia technical occupations (technicians, computer numerical control operators, welders), the technical field (structural engineers, calculators, technical sales people) and occupations in the medically technical field (optician, hearing care professional).¹⁰

The demands on the higher and academic level involve amongst others IT occupations, and occupations in education and teaching. In specifically the care sector indications of shortages are in both very specific occupations and occupations on a higher and academic level as well (nurse practitioners for general practitioners or specialists in geriatric medicine).

IV. THE DUTCH ANSWER TO LABOUR SHORTAGES

The labour migration policy has an almost exclusively demand-driven character in the Netherlands which means that the supply of the labour market within the Netherlands and the EU/EEA come in first to fill the vacancies. An employer can only attract a labour migrant from a third country national when the vacancy cannot be fulfilled by the Dutch or EU/EEA supply. The initiative to attract an employee from a third country lies solely on the employer who also has to take care of a work permit.¹¹ The work permit is subject to a labour market test first to verify the shortages in the Dutch or EU/EEA supply. The bottleneck is that these tests are based on the individual and the present vacancy, so there is no overall focus on the professional sector in these tests. This kind of policy is not set up towards solving labour shortages on a macro-level such as in the USA. Their Green Card system with a supply driven character allows a number of specialized jobs for example to attain a residence permit based on a past or current job (e.g. Afghan/Iraqi translators, broadcasters, and religious workers) independent of the initiative of employers on the US labour market.

The policy for the top levels of the labour market does not have a restrictive character. For the category of knowledge worker the main criteria is an income threshold. Moreover, there is no obliged test to verify the Dutch and EU/EEA labour supply. In the execution of this policy it is also possible for employers to receive a decision on the residence permit application for a knowledge worker within two weeks. These regulations explain the number of applications, namely 10,900 received applications in the knowledge and talent category in 2014 in contrast to the labour migrants category with around 1,700 applica-

¹⁰ European Migration Network

¹¹ The Dutch system has a separate work permit (tewerkstellingsvergunning) and a combined version of the residence and the work permit (GVVA).

tions in the same year. However, although the Dutch policy is more inviting for the top levels, its basis is still demand driven. This demand driven character is further elaborated in the next section.

V. ACKNOWLEDGING THE COMPLEXITY OF THE BLUE CARD

Let us keep in mind that the arrival of the Blue Card marks a remarkable start to combine forces to achieve the desired level of highly skilled workers in the EU. But to become the next attractive continent to work and live in, the Expert Group on Economic Migration already took steps in discussing the complexities of the Blue Card.

One of the complex aspects is the national schemes for highly qualified migrants that exist next to the Blue Card scheme.¹² MS are allowed to run national schemes targeted at highly qualified migrants. These residence permits issued under such national schemes do not confer the same rights of residence in the other MS as provided for in the Blue Card Directive which results in a large number of labour migration schemes across the EU and which affect the level of mobility of the migrant.

Although many issues are highlighted with the preliminary evaluations of the Blue Card (family reunification, attracting graduates/young professionals and so on) one main issue seems to be left out of the discussions, namely the demand driven approach of the Blue Card. The demand driven character indicates that there is no evident macro-level approach to combat the labour shortages in the EU. Due to this system, the potential power of such a regulation is lost, because the initiative is put in the hands of employers to first offer a contract to the highly skilled worker. Therefore, the Blue Card serves the relative small group of migrants who need to cooperate with their employers in order to attain the Blue Card. It may seem that the EU and MS keep control of the labour demand issue, but the flip side of the story shows that EU and the MS have put themselves offside.

VI. ADDITIONAL ISSUES TO TAKE INTO ACCOUNT

The EU discussions about the Blue Card mechanism holds an assumption that the job is the only leading factor for the working migrant, but we need to keep other factors in mind that can be decisive in one's choices and one's life.

One of the factors that need to be discussed is the possible preference to obtain the nationality of a MS rather than the Blue Card. In the case of the Netherlands, a work-

¹² Article 3(4) of the Directive allows this construction.

ing migrant can have the option to become a Dutch citizenship after to have lived for a consecutive period of at least five years in the Netherlands on the basis of a permanent residence permit. A permit on the basis of (highly) qualified work can lead to such a permit with a permanent character. By becoming a Dutch citizen, the migrant automatically achieves mobility within the EU through the right of free movement of persons within the EU territory. Moreover, the rights as a Dutch citizen gives security in terms of e.g. social services, the right to be elected, or the option to become a civil servant. The preference for the Blue Card instead of the Dutch nationality can of course occur if the migrant wants to keep the nationality of the country of origin.¹³

Another factor is the language issue. Obviously, living in a country such as the USA, Canada or Australia comes with less linguistic challenges than living in the majority of MS. Their labour market does not have linguistic restrictions, whereas a migrant who is not fluent in Dutch may not have the same opportunities in the Netherlands as he would have had in the countries with English as the dominant key of communication. Let alone move on a regular base to a country with yet another foreign language to overcome. For the time being, the Blue Card benefits those who are not depending on a certain language proficiency level in their job mobility across the EU, such as positions offered by employers with an international setting such as SAP, MSG, Shell, Philips, Unilever, Lego, Proctor & Gamble, Heineken and so on and those who easily acquire a foreign language.

Social contexts in adult lives can strongly affect the choice to settle in a specific country. Although the Blue Card enables a greater mobility for a migrant worker, one may not prefer this mobility e.g. when raising small children which may to the desire of living in one place or in the same country which diminishes the incentive to opt for a Blue Card. Of course, this does not diminish the contribution of the migrant to enhance the knowledge climate of the country of residence.

Furthermore, the phenomenon of contemporary labour contracts which becomes more and more common on the Dutch labour market has to be taken into account. Although the threshold regarding the term of the contract is set at a minimum of a year, chances should not be ruled out that an amount of these contemporary contracts of less than a year could stand in the way of obtaining the Blue Card.

Finally, key actors to apply for residence permits are often enough (HR) divisions of (international) companies. They are the one who decide for which type of residence permit they will (help to) apply: the Blue Card, a national scheme, or a EC-long term residence permit. It is only logical that a preference for the national scheme continues to exist when thresholds of the national scheme are lower than those of the Blue Card. In the Netherlands, the salary threshold of a so called knowledge migrant is a monthly salary

¹³ In general, a migrant loses the nationality of the country of origin when becoming a Dutch citizen. Moroccan and Turkish migrants are exempted from this rule.

between approximately €3,100 and 4,200 excluding holiday pay¹⁴, whereas the minimum salary for the Blue Card is set at around €4,900 and results in a difference of between approximately €700 and €1,800. Another criteria that reduces a possible preference of the Blue Card is the completion a post-secondary higher education program which is not (yet) a criteria in the knowledge migrant scheme. With the lower thresholds in national regulations, chances very well exist that migrants obtain a residence permit without being (fully) informed or made aware of every existing option. A worthy research subject to look into more closely.

VII. CONCLUSIONS: BUILDING ON AN ATTRACTIVE EUROPE

Commission President Jean Claude Juncker set the goal to make Europe at least as attractive as the favourite migration destinations such as Australia, Canada and the USA. A review of the Blue Card Directive is mostly needed.¹⁵ The question still remains whether changing the criteria of the Blue Card in a more American, Canadian or Australian style and a points based system will lead to more attractiveness. There are arrears to be tackled. The somewhat natural EU tendency toward avoiding risks can increase this backlog as America, Canada and Australia are not waiting for the EU to catch up. Two scenarios are in place.

The first is a careful one with incremental steps. The next step would then be to find more alignment between the different policies of the MS with efficient application processes. Maybe graduate students will be part of the target group. Possible changes in the conditions for the application regard the income threshold combined with relevant work experience. But these kind of amendments will only mean a continuation of the present frame work.

The second scenario is quite bold. In this intervention application for the Blue Card is not only open for the higher segments, but also for the skilled labours. It acknowledges that the bottlenecks of vacancies lie in the shortages of not only highly skilled labour, but in skilled labour as well. It also acknowledges the prognosis that the existing and future labour force is not quantitatively and qualitatively sufficient enough to properly fulfil the vacancies. The boldness can even be extended a step further to implement an additional demand driven system to the supply driven one in order to increase the control on the labour market with a measure on a macro-level.

¹⁴ The salary threshold of knowledge migrants of 30 years and older is set at around €4,200 and that of knowledge migrants younger than 30 years around € 3,200 excluding holiday pay. These standard amounts is adjusted every year.

¹⁵ Expert Group on Economic Migration, *Reviewing the Blue Card Directive*, Brussels, European Commission, 2015.

So what does the future hold? With the economic recess more or less behind us the next decade may as well be to change course in the way we look at migrant labours. Rather than leaving the incentive in the hands of employers, an awareness in the EU decision making process must be achieved in which skilled and highly skilled workers are not only willing to live in the EU due to its attractiveness on the labour market, but in which also is understood that without sufficient employees the EU labour market does not stand a chance in the battle for brains against the USA, Canada and Australia.